

SLL Minimization for Linear Uniformly Excited Sparse Arrays Using Gradient Descent

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Abstract—In this paper, we apply a gradient descent-based method to the synthesis of uniformly excited sparse phased arrays. The effectiveness of gradient-based optimization in this domain is highly dependent on the precision of the Peak Sidelobe Level (PSLL) estimation. Conventional grid-based calculation methods fail to provide the necessary accuracy, introducing numerical noise that prevents efficient convergence. To address this, we implement a grid-less framework for radiation pattern analysis. This approach achieves near-machine precision ($\approx 10^{-16}$) and enhances computational performance compared to traditional discrete grid search. Based on this continuous evaluation, we develop a modified gradient descent strategy capable of synthesizing large-scale arrays. The proposed method manages high-dimensional search spaces and outperforms heuristic algorithms in terms of both convergence speed and the level of sidelobe suppression.

Index Terms—Sparse linear arrays, antenna array synthesis, uniformly excited arrays, sidelobe level (SLL), grid-less optimization, gradient descent, minimax methods, non-convex optimization.

I. INTRODUCTION

The design of large-scale sparse arrays requires the simultaneous optimization of thousands of element positions to minimize the peak sidelobe level (PSLL). Mathematically, this is a high-dimensional minimax problem where gradient-based methods are traditionally considered ineffective due to the non-convex search space and extreme sensitivity to objective function accuracy. Even minor errors in peak detection lead to gradient instability and premature convergence. To ensure stable descent, we maintain the objective function's precision higher than the target gradient tolerance, preventing numerical noise from destabilizing the optimization path near the optimum [6].

Traditional synthesis methods predominantly rely on uniform grid sampling to detect the maximum intensity in the radiation pattern. At the scale of high-precision optimization, these discretization errors act as numerical noise, where the gradient vector oscillates or vanishes near the ridges where sidelobes intersect. To address these challenges, we propose a strategy that replaces grid-based estimation with Newton-type refinement. By exploiting the band-limited properties of the array factor, we ensure the global maximum is captured within an attraction basin and identified with machine-level precision.

To address the challenge of synthesizing large-scale uniformly excited sparse arrays, the proposed gradient-based approach leverages exact directional derivatives to navigate the complex sidelobe landscape. Unlike metaheuristic techniques,

which often suffer from stochastic stagnation and extensive tuning, eliminating discretization noise allows the optimizer to perform a deterministic search for deep sidelobe minima in arrays containing hundreds to thousands of elements. This approach enables the synthesis of large-scale configurations, such as $N = 1000$ and beyond, with stable convergence metrics. The resulting framework outperforms existing heuristic algorithms in suppressive depth, making it suitable for modern satellite and communication systems.

II. SPECTRALLY-INFORMED NEWTON METHOD

Consider a linear array of N coherent isotropic point sources. The characteristics are defined by the parameters:

- $x_j \in [0, 1]$: The normalized spatial coordinate of the j -th element along the array axis, $\mathbf{x} = [x_1, x_2, \dots, x_N]^T$ — the vector of normalized element positions.
- $u = \sin \theta$: The directional sine (spatial frequency), where θ is the angle of observation relative to the broadside.
- $\nu = L/\lambda$: The normalized aperture length in wavelengths.

To simplify the analytical treatment of the interference pattern, we define the quadrature components $C(u)$ and $S(u)$ as the real and imaginary parts of the complex array factor:

$$C(u) = \sum_{j=1}^N \cos(2\pi\nu u x_j), \quad S(u) = \sum_{j=1}^N \sin(2\pi\nu u x_j) \quad (1)$$

The far-field intensity is then given by $I(u) = C^2(u) + S^2(u)$. To compute the gradient and the Hessian, we define the phase term $\phi_j = 2\pi\nu u x_j$ and introduce the first and second-order derivatives of (1) with respect to u :

$$C_u = \sum x_j \cos \phi_j, \quad S_u = \sum x_j \sin \phi_j \quad (2)$$

$$C_{uu} = \sum x_j^2 \cos \phi_j, \quad S_{uu} = \sum x_j^2 \sin \phi_j \quad (3)$$

The derivatives of the quadrature components (1) are:

$$C'(u) = -2\pi\nu S_u, \quad S'(u) = 2\pi\nu C_u \quad (4)$$

$$C''(u) = -(2\pi\nu)^2 C_{uu}, \quad S''(u) = -(2\pi\nu)^2 S_{uu} \quad (5)$$

Substituting these into the derivatives of $I(u)$, we obtain the gradient $I'(u)$ and the Hessian $I''(u)$:

$$I'(u) = 2(CC' + SS') = 4\pi\nu(SC_u - CS_u) \quad (6)$$

$$I''(u) = 8\pi^2\nu^2 [(C_u^2 + S_u^2) - (CC_{uu} + SS_{uu})] \quad (7)$$

The localization of the global maximum of $I(u)$ is performed using the second-order Newton-Raphson iterative scheme. This method exploits the local curvature of the

interference pattern to achieve quadratic convergence. The update rule for the $(m + 1)$ -th iteration is:

$$u^{(m+1)} = u^{(m)} - \frac{I'(u^{(m)})}{I''(u^{(m)})} \quad (8)$$

By substituting the derived gradient and Hessian into the update rule, the final iterative formula for the spatial frequency u is obtained:

$$u^{(m+1)} = u^{(m)} - \frac{1}{2\pi\nu} \frac{SC_u - CS_u}{(C_u^2 + S_u^2) - (CC_{uu} + SS_{uu})} \quad (9)$$

The number of iterations is set to five based on empirical observations. This fixed value will be applied in the subsequent sections and will remain consistent for all datasets presented in this paper.

The array factor constitutes a finite sum of complex exponentials with spatial frequencies governed by the array physical aperture. Consequently, the normalized radiation intensity $I(u) = |AF(u)|^2$ represents an exponential sum characterized by bounded spectral support. Its derivative $I'(u)$ is likewise an exponential sum whose maximum spatial frequency is structurally bounded by the total aperture parameter ν . Based on classical spectral results for exponential sums with real frequencies [4], the cardinality and distribution of zeros within a specified domain are fundamentally bounded by the frequency spectrum span. Specifically, for an exponential sum with a maximum spatial frequency ν , the total number of stationary points scales proportionally with ν .

Although modern bounds demonstrate that this frequency threshold can be formally exceeded by a term proportional to the cardinality of the frequency set [5], such high-frequency oscillations require extreme coefficient distributions and exhibit negligible amplitudes. For physically realizable sparse array configurations, the number of energetically significant stationary points of $I(u)$ within the visible region $u \in [0, 1]$ scales as $\lceil \nu \rceil$. While these extrema are non-uniformly distributed across the search space, fundamental bounds on exponential sums imply a strict limitation on the maximum curvature of $I(u)$, ensuring that any significant sidelobe peak maintains a finite minimum spatial width proportional to $1/(2\nu)$.

Based on the bound on the number of stationary points, the sampling step is chosen as:

$$\Delta u = \frac{1}{4\lceil \nu \rceil} \quad (10)$$

Since the number of extrema of $I(u)$ on the interval $[0, 1]$ does not exceed 2ν , the average spacing between adjacent extrema is at least $1/(2\nu)$. The chosen step therefore oversamples this spacing by a factor of two, ensuring that each interval between consecutive grid points contains at most one extremum and that at least one initial point falls within the attraction basin of every significant local maximum. As a result, the Newton-Raphson iterations initialized from this grid provide a high probability of convergence to all local maxima

Fig. 1: (a) Computational performance: execution time vs. number of sources N compared to uniform grid search (10^5 points); (b) Numerical accuracy analysis: absolute error relative to high-precision ground truth (mpmath), demonstrating stable machine-level precision.

III. COMPUTATIONAL PERFORMANCE AND NUMERICAL PRECISION

The computational complexity of the proposed method is $O(\nu \cdot N)$. In contrast, the complexity of conventional grid-based detection scales as $O(\text{gridsize} \cdot N)$. Given that $\nu \ll \text{gridsize}$ in practical applications, the proposed approach offers a significant reduction in compared computational to the exhaustive grid search.

To evaluate the performance (Fig. 1a and Fig. 1b) of the proposed method, a benchmark study was conducted over a range of array sizes $N \in [10, 10^4]$ and $\nu = 100$ search area is restricted to the interval $u \in [1/\nu, 1]$ for each configuration, element positions were randomly generated using a uniform distribution. The reference solution (ground truth) was computed independently using arbitrary-precision arithmetic (mpmath with 60 decimal digits). Specifically, the sidelobe level was obtained by locating all stationary points of the intensity function via root-finding applied to its derivative, followed by selecting the global maximum. The proposed framework and a uniform grid search baseline were evaluated in terms of execution time and numerical fidelity. To provide a competitive baseline, the grid search utilized a dense uniform sampling of 10^5 points.

As illustrated in Fig. 1a and Fig. 1b, the proposed method provides approximately a 20-fold reduction in execution time compared to the grid-based approach across the entire range of N . Furthermore, the proposed method decouples execution time from numerical precision. While the grid search is limited by a discretization error floor near 10^{-8} , the proposed approach reaches machine precision ($\approx 10^{-16}$) with lower computational overhead.

TABLE I: Numerical Stability and Error Distribution

Config.		Median	99th	Maximum	Rel.
N	ν	Error	Perc.	Error	(%)
10	22	1.94×10^{-16}	2.57×10^{-15}	7.21×10^{-9}	99.99
16	40	2.44×10^{-16}	2.76×10^{-15}	4.10×10^{-6}	99.99
20	15	8.56×10^{-17}	1.00×10^{-15}	2.00×10^{-7}	99.99
32	16	5.19×10^{-17}	6.38×10^{-16}	7.77×10^{-10}	99.99
32	100	3.26×10^{-16}	4.75×10^{-15}	5.78×10^{-15}	100.00

* Reliability: Err < 10^{-14} . Trials: 10,000 for each configurations.

The numerical stability of the proposed framework was tested across several configurations, with results summarized in Table I. The data reveals that for all tested scenarios, the median absolute error remains at the level of machine epsilon, confirming the theoretical advantage of a discretization-free approach.

IV. OPTIMIZATION PSLL

For all optimized configurations, a minimum inter-element spacing of 0.5λ was strictly enforced to ensure physical realizability. The synthesis of a sparse array to minimize the peak sidelobe level is formulated as a non-smooth minimax optimization problem: $\min_{\mathbf{x}} \text{PSLL}(\mathbf{x})$ where the objective function is explicitly defined as $\text{PSLL}(\mathbf{x}) = \max_{u \in S} I(u, \mathbf{x})$, and S denotes the sidelobe region excluding the main lobe bounds. Let u_{\max} represent the spectral coordinate of the single dominant peak isolated at the current iteration. According to Danskin's theorem for minimax problems [7], the directional derivative of this minimax objective function with respect to the element coordinates \mathbf{x} can be practically approximated by the spatial gradient of the continuous intensity evaluated at this maximum point:

$$\nabla_{\mathbf{x}} \text{PSLL}(\mathbf{x}) \approx \nabla_{\mathbf{x}} I(u_{\max}, \mathbf{x}). \quad (11)$$

The physical rationale for this analytical formulation is governed by the piecewise-smooth nature of the minimax cost surface. The objective function consists of multiple smooth manifolds where each hyper-surface corresponds to a specific sidelobe peak. These manifolds intersect at non-differentiable ridges where multiple sidelobes achieve identical peak intensities. In minimax optimization theory [3], the optimal equiripple configuration typically resides strictly on these non-smooth intersections.

We deliberately avoid smooth approximations, such as the Soft-Max (Log-Sum-Exp) function: $\text{PSLL}_{\text{smooth}}(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{\alpha} \ln \sum e^{\alpha I_k}$. Numerical experiments indicate that achieving the necessary synthesis precision via the Soft-Max approximation requires a scaling parameter α exceeding 200. In high-dimensional search spaces, such extreme values tend to induce numerical instability, which justifies the preference for our direct minimax optimization strategy.

The proposed algorithm is based on a modified gradient descent approach with an adaptive step size modification:

$$\mathbf{d} \propto \frac{\nabla_{\mathbf{x}} \text{PSLL}(\mathbf{x})}{\|\nabla_{\mathbf{x}} \text{PSLL}(\mathbf{x})\|} \cdot \left[\frac{1}{\|\nabla_{\mathbf{x}} \text{PSLL}(\mathbf{x})\|} \right]_{d_0}^1 \quad (12)$$

This adaptation accelerates the convergence on flat plateaus where $\text{PSLL}(\mathbf{x})$ is maximal, while simultaneously dampening the step size in regions close to the local minima where $\|\nabla_{\mathbf{x}} \text{PSLL}(\mathbf{x})\|$ typically exhibits higher values. While an upper bound on the step size prevents overshooting and instability at non-differentiable zones, a lower bound is imposed on the step size to ensure the search point maintains a sufficient effective step size when moving between peaks of the $\text{PSLL}(\mathbf{x})$. Under this modification, the optimization point effectively navigates between various competing peaks until it reaches the intersection of multiple manifolds within the

Fig. 2: Peak PSLL vs. number of elements. The search zone is defined as $[1/\nu, 1]$. The curves correspond to average element spacing ρ . Minimum inter-element spacing of 0.5λ

$\text{PSLL}(\mathbf{x})$ objective space, the search point tracks along the intersection of these active manifolds until it encounters a junction with an additional constraint and so it repeats. These intersection points correspond to the equilibrium state where multiple sidelobes in the radiation pattern $I(u)$ reach the same peak level, effectively forming the equiripple floor.

For configurations where the number of elements N is sufficiently large (specifically $N > 50$ in this implementation), the initial point is not selected randomly. Instead, the spatial density of the elements is initialized to mimic a Taylor distribution profile. A random noise is then added to this initial distribution to accelerate the convergence rate. This approach is based on the principle of density tapering, where PSLL suppression is achieved by modulating the element spacing rather than the excitation amplitude, effectively approximating a continuous Taylor aperture taper [2].

As illustrated in Fig. 2, increasing the number of elements N for a fixed main lobe region $[-1/\nu, 1/\nu]$ leads to a numerical plateau at approximately -20.9 dB across various average element spacings $\rho = \nu/N$. This convergence suggests that the threshold represents a fundamental physical limit of the aperture's spatial bandwidth rather than an algorithmic constraint. Specifically, once the equiripple state is achieved, the PSLL becomes largely invariant to further increases in element count N , being governed primarily by the total aperture length and the specified beamwidth. While Dolph-Chebyshev limits are derived for periodic arrays, our results show sparse configurations converge to a similar floor, though formal theoretical establishment of this boundary is still required.

To overcome the limit of approximately -20.9 dB observed under strict beamwidth constraints, the main lobe exclusion region in this study is set to $u \in [1.5/\nu, 1]$. We benchmark our results against the DELF [9] and CGDE [12] algorithms, though it should be noted that a direct numerical comparison is sensitive to the specific main lobe exclusion criteria, which are not explicitly standardized in prior literature. To ensure reproducibility, the complete source code, hyperparameters, and optimized coordinates for all cases are available on GitHub at <https://github.com/ArtOreh/High-Precision-Sparse-Array-Synthesis>.

The performance of the proposed optimization is summa-

TABLE II: Comparative Synthesis Results of PSLL: Benchmarking Against DELF (2018) and CGDE (2024)

Case	N	ν	DELF (2018) [9]		CGDE (2024) [12]		Proposed Method		
			Best [dB]	Mean [dB]	Best [dB]	Mean [dB]	Best [dB]	Mean [dB]	Time [s]
A	152	98.5	-24.1	-23.8	-24.22	-23.93	-23.27	-23.20	76.1
B	132	90.5	-24.9	-23.8	-25.46	-24.36	-25.81	-25.74	53.5
C	78	73.0	-20.6	-18.7	-23.01	-20.18	-23.71	-23.53	28.5
D	251	250.5	-22.7	-22.4	—	—	-27.68	-27.54	325.5
Large	400	300.0	—	—	—	—	-30.97	-30.85	905.0
Sat.	600	450.0	—	—	—	—	-31.12	-31.07	2573.6
Over.	1000	750.0	—	—	—	—	-31.13	-31.10	9934.0

Note: All proposed results are obtained averaged over 10 independent trials. The “—” symbols indicate that results were not reported for these aperture sizes in the respective literature. Hardware: Intel Core i5-8400 (3.90 GHz).

Fig. 3: Radiation pattern for $N = 600, L = 450\lambda$. Peak SLL of -31.12 dB is achieved in the optimization zone $u \in [1.5/\nu, 1]$, minimum inter-element spacing of 0.5λ . The magnified inset illustrates the main lobe integrity and the initial sidelobe floor transition.

rized in Table II. For the Case D configuration ($N = 251, \nu = 250.5\lambda$), we report a PSLL of -27.68 dB, representing a 5 dB improvement over prior results.

The scalability of the method is further demonstrated in Fig. 3 for the $N = 600$ case, where a uniform sidelobe floor of -31.12 dB is maintained without beam distortion. It should be noted that for such large apertures, fixed-grid discretization is highly susceptible to missing narrow sidelobe peaks and may lead to main beam splitting. The evaluation framework avoids these issues, providing reliable tracking of the radiation pattern’s extrema. The framework’s scalability was further verified for $N = 3000$ ($\rho = 0.75$). This case converged to the ≈ -31.1 dB floor, confirming the method’s asymptotic stability and the physical nature of the saturation limit at extreme scales.

V. CONCLUSION

In this work, we presented a grid-less framework for the synthesis of large-scale uniformly excited sparse linear arrays. The core of the proposed approach lies in a rigorous method for PSLL evaluation that bypasses the accuracy limitations of traditional grid-based sampling. By integrating the proposed PSLL evaluation into a modified gradient descent framework, we achieve an optimization process that consistently converges to stable solutions compared to conventional benchmarks. Numerical results demonstrate that this framework leads to significant performance gains, including a 5 dB improvement in SLL suppression for standard test cases. Furthermore, the

algorithm exhibits robust scalability, handling massive configurations of up to $N = 3000$ elements. The high stability and negligible variance between independent trials confirm that reliable PSLL tracking is essential for effective optimization in high-dimensional search spaces. The study also provides numerical evidence of a PSLL saturation floor that appears to be independent of element density, pointing toward a potential physical limit of the aperture that warrants further theoretical investigation.

Current efforts are directed toward extending this framework to two-dimensional planar arrays. Preliminary analysis indicates that maintaining exact peak detection will be equally vital for managing the increased complexity and degrees of freedom inherent in 2D sparse architectures.

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